

**AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE AND
SHAREHOLDER RETURN FACTORS IN FTSE 100 COMPANIES**

**A Dissertation Submitted in Part-fulfillment of the
Requirements for the Degree of Master of Business
Administration of the
University of Warwick**

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**Student Name: VALERY MANOKHIN
ID Number: 0262118
Date: November 2010**

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1 The executive summary

This dissertation and study focused on one of the long-standing debates in the academia and business as to what drives firm performance. Following development of resource-based view the focus of strategic management has been shifting out of prescriptions formerly provided by industrial organizations frameworks towards building sustainable set of firm resources to underpin sustainable competitive advantage.

This study analyzed the sources of variability in performance of major UK firms, as represented by FTSE 100 index, to determine existence and relative contributions among other of industry and firm specific factors.

Substantial body of academic literature was reviewed to determine and optimize approach to study empirical performance of FTSE 100 firm data over the most recent 5-year period of time. The time period was substantially impacted by recent economic developments arising out of credit crisis followed by economic contraction on a scale unseen since the Great Depression. The findings from the study thus represent interest in both that they covered major UK firms unlike previous research which focused predominantly on US companies as well as most recent and unique period of time. In the current uncertain economic environment the findings thus can provide additional insight as no company can expect good performance just because of global economic boom enjoyed in the previous several years.

The study examined firm performance by both utilizing statistical tools as well as rigorous application of variance component analysis to optimized model fitted to address both previous research and findings on the subject matter as well as availability of data.

The results obtain from statistical examination and estimation of model demonstrated importance of both industry and firm specific factors. The findings were generally in line with previous research on the subject and presented a more balanced practical view. In addition, a link between firm performance and shareholder returns was examined in more detail and a number of observations were made specifying additional hurdles which need to be cleared by firms in order to deliver truly excellent shareholder returns.

2 The introduction

This dissertation examines sources of performance differences by applying theoretical and empirical tools developed by several authors in analyzing predominantly US firms to the set of major UK firms as represented by FTSE 100 index component companies. Examining sources of performance differences has long been one of the main issues in both theoretical and applied strategic management studies following emergence and development of industrial organization, strategy and resource based theories of the firm and firm performance.

The objectives of the dissertation are to analyze the sources of performance variability in FTSE 100 index component firms, including relative contributions of industry and firm specific factors. Additionally, the pattern of relative contribution of industry vs. firm specific factors is examined for various industry sectors which in combination represent the index of leading UK listed companies.

Chapter 3 outlines a number of theoretical and applied research projects undertaken in the area, mostly by US authors who either developed theoretical models and concepts or analysed various samples of US companies' data in order to address long standing strategy debate of what is driving firms' performance as well as relative contribution of such drivers. The development of industrial organization, strategy and resource-based views of thinking was simultaneously contributing to and stimulating this debate in order to address one of the central questions in maximizing value of the firm as well as in order to develop management models, concepts and tools to allow for and facilitate achievement of such objective. The issue of performance drivers is thus of substantial interest to both management studies scholars and managers of listed and private companies.

In Chapter 4 tools previously utilized by leading US and European researchers to examine relative sources of performance in samples of US companies data are applied to UK FTSE 100 index constituents' data. As outlined in Chapter 3 the methodology for such analysis evolved over time to both incorporate various modeling tools and to allow utilization of available data. This dissertation examines data available for FTSE 100 firms by looking at 5-year performance and other metrics. Such approach is considered to be optimal, given both results of review of models previously used in analyzing US company data (as outlined in Chapter 3) as well as availability of relevant data set for UK companies. The importance of FTSE 100 constituents for both the UK economy and globally further supports objectives of this examination and selection of relevant data set.

Chapter 5 presents results of this study by outlining performance differences and their underlying drivers among FTSE 100 firms, including comparisons by industry.

Chapter 6 discusses results and findings from this study, including whether previous results obtained predominantly by examination of US firms' data are broadly in line with

findings from this study examining variability in performance of major listed UK firms. It also presents recommendations and conclusions arising from the review.

Chapter 7 states limitations of the review taking into account issues previously raised in the literature as well as limits arising from this specific study. It sets out proposals for further additional research in the area.

3 The literature review

The field of strategic management has been developed over substantial period of time with the term “strategy” itself starting to develop into distinct management study field in the 1960s. During 1960s the basis terms and definitions of strategy took place. The field has experienced further substantial progression in the 1970s accompanied by rise of global consulting firms such as McKinsey, BCG and Bain, which contributed substantially to the development of strategic management frameworks and their applications in practice (e.g. BCG’s “experience curve” and “growth-share” matrix). Parallel to applied development of strategic management field substantial amount of theoretical research took place in the 1970s, focusing on application of research methods, including econometrics, to the studies of actual situations mostly by research groups of Harvard and Purdue universities.

BCG matrix

The BCG matrix is an applied strategic management tool that had been created by Bruce Henderson of BCG in 1968 in order to help corporations analyze their business units or product lines. This model helps a company to allocate resources across strategic business units (SBU) and is widely used in brand marketing, product management, strategic management, and portfolio analysis.

The model and its applications are widely known both to management and academics and are thus not described here in detail for these reasons. The model represents one of tools used in so-called portfolio management framework.

During the 1980s the field experienced substantial development growth with Michael Porter's pioneering work *Competitive Strategy* (1980) defining and developing a novel approach by focusing at the competitive landscape of industries and firms positions within companies.

The Porter's five forces model is briefly reviewed below based on Porter (2008) as it is an essential tool in analysing industry influence on a firm's performance, enabling to evaluate industry's competitive structure as well as providing substantial insight into Porter's theories.

The Five Forces That Shape Industry Competition

from "The Five Competitive Forces That Shape Strategy" by Michael E. Porter, *Harvard Business Review*, January 2008

According to Porter, performance of an industry is predominantly shaped by its structure, which in turn influences performance of firms within this industry. Whilst both theoretical and practical research developed after Porter's groundbreaking model have been developed and widely accepted have somewhat diminished the focus and conclusions of the model, Porter's framework remains solidly embedded into set of tools used by management of companies, strategy consultants and academia. Even in industries where performance variability is mostly driven by firm specific factors the model could be used to explain and analyse a portion of variance attributed to industry and its structure.

Porter (1980) concludes that despite the fact that industries vary significantly from each other, the fundamental factors described below determine industry structure, degree of industry competition and these in turn substantially drive profitability returns available to industry participants. In his 2008 paper (Porter (2008)) the author illustrates, using 14-year returns from a sample of US firms, that intensity of competitive forces in industries such as airlines, textiles and hotels make it very difficult for almost any firm to earn an attractive return on investment. Such view is both generally consistent with performance demonstrated by sectors above as held by general public and professional investment community. Indeed, arguably one of the most well known investors of our time, Warren Buffet, has made the following comment about airline industry in his 2008 letter to Berkshire Hathaway shareholders:

“The worst sort of business is one that grows rapidly, requires significant capital to engender the growth, and then earns little or no money. Think airlines. Here a durable competitive advantage has proven elusive ever since the days of the Wright Brothers. Indeed, if a farsighted capitalist had been present at Kitty Hawk, he would have done his successors a huge favour by shooting Orville down.”

Whilst the language of quotation is reflective of Buffett’s style, the essence of the comment indeed highlights the nature of the industry, where majority of participants either go through periodic restructuring funded by taxpayer (e.g. US Chapter 11) or are supported by governments (Europe). With a very few exceptions majority of airlines historically consistently destroyed shareholder value, with even most successful airlines currently providing either negative returns or only moderate returns – e.g. Southwest Airlines and Ryanair returning -14% and 18% accordingly over the last 5 years.

On the other side Porter cites successful industries such as software, soft drinks and toiletries, where many companies have been historically profitable.

Porter’s five forces:

- 1) **Threat of new entrants** – as investors are able to allocate capital to profitable and growing industries in the presence of excess returns, the threat of competition is mitigated by so-called barriers to entry of which Porter lists 7 as example. The degree of protection afforded by such barriers should be assessed on a relative basis vis-a-vis capital and innovation capabilities of new entrants.
- 2) **The power of suppliers** – the relative importance of suppliers vis-a-vis industry could allow suppliers capture higher value thus undermining industry structure and profitability especially if switching costs are high or suppliers offer products without substitutes, are differentiated or there is a risk of forward integration by suppliers.
- 3) **The power of buyers** – powerful or demanding customers can appropriate value away from the industry especially if there are few powerful buyers, switching costs are low, the product has little effect on buyer’s other costs, buyers are cost-sensitive, cash strapped and product represents significant fraction in buyers’ cost structures.

- 4) **Threat of substitutes** – the threat of substitutes is especially high if they offer similar or better performance at same or better price. Substitutes not only limit prices which can be charged to industry customers but increase costs, for example in developing quality product propositions in order to better service customers.
- 5) **Rivalry among existing competitors** – Porter makes a point by highlighting that rivalry is especially destructive if it focuses solely on price because competition transfers profits directly from industry to its customers. This is in contrast to other forms of competition and is well known fact to managers in various industries. In consumer goods industries, for example, companies often limit retail price whilst competing on other non-price dimensions such as marketing and promotions (advertising, coupons, prizes etc.).

The combination of forces above manifests itself in industry structure and intensity of industry competition, which itself determines long-run industry profit potential as economic value created by industry is either bargained away or ideally captured by industry players. The industry structure proves to be relatively stable over time with profitability differences remarkably persistent, albeit as demonstrated many times over even more stable industries (e.g. pharmaceuticals) can sometimes undergo sudden and significant transformations with speed of change likely to accelerate going forward due to ongoing technological developments, innovation and emergence of new players (e.g. China, India and Brazil). The factors above can both accelerate the pace of change and transform the industries dramatically within short periods of time (e.g. established and entrenched movie rental chain Blockbuster seeking Chapter 11 protection as a result of its business model been displaced by fundamental changes in the way in which consumers enjoy entertainment, as well as due to more lifestyles catered better by more agile emerging players – in this case mail DVD rental companies like Amazon and LoveFilm).

At the same time, Porter's five forces model, whilst very straightforward and relatively simple should not be used in a mechanical manner, indeed in his article author both clarifies potential pitfalls and advises that applications of the model are more wide than could be seen at the outset, e.g. by the ability and responsibility of industry leaders to maintain, shape and develop industry structure to avoid its changing in a detrimental way, either through changing consumers tastes or through emergence of new players, both transforming and undermining the industry. In the example above, it could be argued within the model's framework, that Blockbuster had enough time and resources to both foresee and counter competitive threats by addressing the ways consumers enjoy delivery of their entertainment by utilising its market position and scale (lower sourcing costs), developing alternative delivery channels (website + mail) and releasing and returning capital to its shareholders (substantial presence on high street in both UK and US allowed plenty of time to dispose of properties during previous real estate boom years).

Critics of “5 Forces” model point that the concept includes choice of specific five forces as well as forces’ substantial variation in particular industry situations.

Kay (1993) points to evidence that company’s performance within an industry is far more determined by firm-specific factors rather than conditions within and outside that industry, whilst one of the leading strategists Ohmae (1998) observed that strategy is not about “beating the competitions” but is about “serving customers real needs”.

Despite the importance of Porter’s “5 Forces” model and its widespread popularity in both academic management studies and practical applications, debate in strategy has long been focused on whether performance differences among firms were mostly determined by industry (as illustrated by Porter’s model) or could be attributed to other firm-specific factors. More recently alternative school of thinking emerged which is sometimes called resource-base view, in this view industry structure is seen as less important than historical specific factors which gives rise to firms’ differences and account for differentials in firms’ performance. Proponents of this school counter that focusing too much on industry structure and positioning detract from the fact that in order to build or protect market positions both specific and costly resources are required in order to both underpin and defend industry structure by linking unique resources with market/product positions. Such linking of resources and market positions is needed to utilise opportunities and mitigate threats existing in the firms’ competitive environment in order to sustain competitive advantage and achieve good performance. Given the importance of this view and its significant relevance for the topic of this dissertation the resource-base view is covered in more details below.

Resource-based view

The resource-base view essentially advocates that firms should determine the set of unique resources and capabilities which they possess and find an environment in which to best exploit these assets. Examples of resource cited by various authors include brands, business processes, access to physical resources, unique and specific competencies.

Systematic and influential way of looking at the resources of the firm could be seen in Wernerfelt (1984), however origins of the resource-based view can be traced back to earlier research by several authors including works by Coase (1937), Selznick (1957), Penrose (1959), Stigler (1961), Chandler (1962, 1977), and Williamson (1975). A fundamental view pointed by some authors was that resources and product represent “two sides of the same coin”. Wernerfelt defined resource as “anything which could be thought of as strength or weakness of a given firm” and cited examples of resources such as brands, technology, personnel, trade contacts, machinery, procedures, capital etc. The paper further defined and explored concepts of resource position barriers and resource-product

matrices following analogy with previously developed concepts of product-market positioning developed by BCG etc.

Barney (1991) further developed and systematised concepts of resource-based view by looking in more substance at a link between firm's resources and sustainable competitive advantage as well as qualities required of firm's attributes in order to be considered resources and have potential to generate competitive advantage:

- *Valuable* - A resource must enable a firm to deploy a value-creating strategy, by either outperforming its competitors or alternatively reduce its own weaknesses. Thus attributes of a firm only become resources when they neutralize threats or exploit and capitalize on the opportunities in a firm's environment.
- *Rare* - To be of value, a resource must by definition be rare. Resources possessed by large number of competitors simultaneously deploying common strategy by exploiting common resource do not lead to competitive advantage(s) for these firms.
- *In-imitable* - If a valuable and rare resource is controlled by only one firm it could be a source of a competitive advantage. This advantage could be sustainable only if competitors are not able to duplicate this strategic asset perfectly. The term isolating mechanism was introduced by Rumelt (1984, p567) to explain why firms might not be able to imitate a resource to the degree that they are able to compete with the firm having the valuable resource.
- *Non-substitutable* - Even if a resource is rare, potentially value-creating and imperfectly imitable, an equally important aspect is lack of substitutability. If competitors are able to counter firm's value-creating strategy with a substitute, prices are driven down to the point that price equals discounted future rents, thus resulting in zero economic profits.

Barney (1991) further looked at the factors surrounding acquisition of rare and in-imitable resources and concluded that it is generally not possible to obtain resource advantages through competitive markets, unless such markets are imperfect. Such conclusions can also be arrived at by using tools developed in industry analysis above similar to the approach used by Wernerfelt (1984), where in the presence of competitive environment prices of resources will be bid up to the levels nullifying net economic profits available from utilisation of these resources through deploying of competitive strategies in the product-markets arenas. Further Barney (1991) concluded that firms seeking to obtain above normal returns must be consistently better informed about value of these resources by having more accurate expectations and that it is generally not possible to obtain resource advantages through the analysis of competitive environment. As an alternative Barney (1991) advocated that firms could be lucky by inadvertently acquiring and deploying resources, the benefits of which later turn out to exceed acquisition costs.

Dierickx and Cool (1989) outlined limitations of Barney's model by pointing out that not all factors can be bought and sold and also pointing to incomplete nature of strategic factor markets. Factors such as reputation, loyalty, specific skills can now be bought or sold but instead must be accumulated by firm following appropriate time path of flows over time. Critical or strategic assets stocks are those non-tradable resources which also meet requirements of non-imitability and non-substitutability. Authors introduce several concepts to explain which factors make it difficult to imitate assets stocks by competitors:

- *Time compression diseconomies* – doubling the flow of resource, whilst shortening time is manifestation of “law of diminishing returns” previously long known in microeconomics when one of the resources is held constant. Indeed studies demonstrate that doubling R&D efforts over half-time interval produces smaller increment to stock of R&D.
- *Asset mass efficiencies* – given a high level of asset stock makes it easier to increase stock level, when compared to smaller initial resource level. The concept is related to network effect, manifesting in increasing the value of product or service as more and more people use it.
- *Interconnectedness of asset stocks* – increase in the level of one stock may depend not just on the level of this stock, but also on the levels of related stocks, thus making it difficult for some firms to catch up if they are lacking other asset stocks.
- *Asset erosion* – all assets decay over time, including R&D, customer loyalty and technological advantage. To credibly deter entry leader firms must have substantial reserve of important asset stocks and also rebuild them more quickly through the effects above.
- *Casual ambiguity* – the process of asset accumulation cannot always be deterministic and in some industries (e.g. pharmaceuticals) is more of a probabilistic nature. Thus R&D expenditure impacts probabilities of accumulating assets stocks rather than their levels directly. It could be argued, similar process is observed in oil exploration companies with some junior companies consistently striking oil more often than others (e.g. Cairn Energy).

In addition to potential threats of imitability, assets stocks substitution can render assets obsolete (e.g. Xerox service network following successful challenge by Cannon which focused instead on compact easy-to-use models). The authors argue that complementary framework is required to evaluate the stream of quasi-rents arising from deployment of resources for sustainable competitive advantage and performance. The strategy is thus in the selection of optimal path of flows for accumulation of asset stocks whilst performance and potential profitability are determined by level of stocks.

The authors argue that asset stocks which could be bought and sold can not be sources of long-term rents as otherwise such assets could be purchased by rivals. The authors emphasize the importance of assets which cannot be purchased (such as learning-by-

doing, organisational culture etc) and hence are more likely to be specific to the firm. As shown in Conner (1991) such specific assets are more likely to be bound more strongly to the firm and because of such specificity provide a source of long-term rents.

Dierickx and Cool (1989) conclude that inconclusive results of prior studies of performance could be explained by failure to distinguish between flows and stocks as using only flow variables precludes unequivocal results.

Barney (2001) offers additional perspective by comparing resource-based view with neoclassical school and evolutionary economics models. In particular it is interesting to note that the only substantial difference from Ricardo's neo-classical model is inelastic supply for resources (factors of production in classical microeconomics) with firms being unable to expand supply of resources despite increasing practice due to incomplete markets (Dierickx and Cool (1989)).

Peteraf (1993) offers additional insight into resource-based view by introducing key conditions, which all have to be met for a firm to have sustainable competitive advantage:

- *Heterogeneity* – resource bundles and competencies differ across firms. Firms endowed with more “efficient resources” are able to produce more economically and/or better satisfy customer needs. In the market where supply of such efficient resources is limited it is possible for efficient firms to earn profits (“Ricardo rents”) even without limiting output (“Monopoly rents”). Peteraf (1993) revisits basic Ricardo models to demonstrate the effects of limited “efficient resources” on firms’ profits. Whilst Ricardo’s model was initially developed for basic class or resources, including capital and labour, in modern models above (Barney (1991), Dierickx and Cool (1989), Prahalad and Hamel (1990)) the notion of limited resource is extended to other classes of resources (reputation, skills, competencies etc) .
- *Ex post limits to competition* – even in the presence of limited resources sustainability depends on the limits to competition for those rents. In the resource-based view the focus is on imperfect imitability and imperfect substitution of efficient resources (Barney (1991)).
- *Imperfect mobility* – resource are perfectly immobile if they can not be traded, specialized to firm-specific needs or transaction costs associated with their transfer are increasingly high. Such resources cannot be bid away readily from their employer and remain bound to the firm and available for use for very long period of time.
- *Ex ante limits to competition* – there must be limited competition for establishing inimitable resource position by rivals. Ex ante competition for resources can bid up the value of resources and dissipate rents to zero.

A major contribution of this resource-base model is that it could be used to explain long-lived differences in firm’s performance that can not be attributed to variability in industry

conditions and is thus especially useful for this research. As outlined later in this section there is substantial body of research (Schmalensee (1985), Rumelt (1991)) empirically demonstrating that substantial part of performance variability is not explained by industry. Whilst this model is difficult to apply in empirical studies due to lack of clarity as to how to isolate and measure specific factors above, it could be practically useful to managers seeking to understand, build or extent competitive advantage.

Prahalad and Hamel (1990) introduced the concept of “core competencies” and demonstrated by example that firms which focused on acquisition and development of core competencies were able to achieve successful performance by developing portfolios of core products enabling to successfully position end products in relevant markets. In contrast firms which neglected core competencies and focused instead on management of SBUs as prescribed by portfolio theories have lost their competitive advantage and positions through loss of relevant skills and technologies enabling them to continue meeting demand of customers and changing markets. Prahalad and Hamel (1990) outlined four key concepts in relation to core competencies:

- *Corporate span* – Core competencies span and support several businesses and products in a corporation.
- *Temporal dominance* – Products are but a temporal expression of core competencies. Whilst products change, core competencies are more stable and evolving slower compared to products.
- *Learning by doing* – Competencies are acquired and built on through the collective learning process of organization.
- *Competitive locus* – Authors observe that competitive behavior in products/markets is superficial expression of deeper competition over core competencies. Inter-firm competition is thus competition over acquisition of skills.

Conner (1991) provides an interesting insight in terms of looking at resource-based view and comparing it with different models of industrial organisation (IO). The author argues that resource-based approach is “reaching for a theory of the firm” and is both similar and differs from IO models. The author offers interesting insight into relative value of resource for a firm to which resource is specific by constructing a simple but insightful model – in particular the value of resource is related to the linkage of resource to a firm’s existing asset base and especially the relative strength of that linkage compared to what competitors would achieve. Such linkage is central to the notion of rents and constitutes the constraints on the input investments of the firms in this situation. The second situation is related to the notion of first-mover advantage whereby firm is able to secure resources before competitors attempt to obtain them either due to luck or brilliance. The analysis here, whilst using different theoretical constructs, is similar to that of Barney (1986) and Peteraf (1993) discussed above. The author concludes that resource-based view is unique in comparison to the IO approaches in that it constitutes theory of the firm. In terms of practical application the author makes an interesting observation which could be best

summarised by direct quote “it appears that reliable measure of underlying resources pose a heavy burden on empirics” which make practical applications of theory quite difficult.

Nelson (1991) argues that divisions between how economists and students of firm management view firms stems from the fact that from particular theoretical view of firm behaviour. If one instead took an evolutionary view about economic activity then firm differences matter importantly regarding issues which traditionally have been of interest to economics. Firm diversity is thus an important characteristic of the processes that create economical and social progress. Similar to arguments deployed by Wernerfelt (1984) and Conner (1991) economics and resource-based view share more similarities than normally thought.

Conner and Prahalad (1996) revisit resource-based theory through further development of resource-based knowledge-based theory of the firm. In particular authors apply Coase’s (1937) general standard for the firm theory: why do firms exist and what determined their scope and scale. The authors deliberately stay away from opportunistic transactions costs arguments and arguments to determine whether resource-based view has standalone basis to qualify for firm theory. The authors argue that firms can exist because of knowledge-based transaction costs that are independent of opportunistic considerations explored by Williamson and whilst resource-based view should not be seen as exclusive framework answering Coase’s fundamental questions its application provides fuller realisation of Coase’s original insights as to *raison d’etre* for firm organisation. The authors argue and demonstrate on the basis of a model that in order to understand the theories of why firms and their performance differs an understanding is required of why activity is organised into firms as opposed to through arms-length markets as the former should include the latter as an essential component. The knowledge-based effects can outweigh opportunistic motives in terms of firm organisation where opportunistic effect is too small or market contracting vis-a-vis firm organisation if only opportunistic arguments were taken into account. The authors introduce two new concepts “knowledge substitution” and “the flexibility effect” (the costs of altering responsibilities in response to changed conditions) and argue that assuming bounded rationality alone (limited ability of individuals to store, process and transfer knowledge and information) create knowledge substitution effect in firms whereby employees can perform certain task using knowledge of more skilled supervisors before they have fully understood and internalised such knowledge. In comparison arms-length’s market contractors would usually perform procedures and tasks in line with their established understanding and routines. Knowledge substitution thus create a form “internal synergy” whereby employees can benefit firm’s performance through positive effects of knowledge gained from their more senior colleagues thus benefiting organisation as a whole. The organisational mode selected will thus depend upon benefits arising from knowledge substitution effect (generally higher when knowledge differential between supervisors and employees is higher) and the costs of operating in each mode, i.e. firm organisation versus market-based contracting. The authors argue and demonstrate that, contrary to some views, the more dynamic and uncertain is competitive environment, the more firm organization is likely to be preferred as opposed to market-based contracts. This is due to the fact that in such environment the costs of renegotiation of contracts could be quite high, the

framework thus supports the notion that firm organisation offers firm stability of vision and strategic intent (Hamel and Prahalad (1989)).

Resource based choice of organisational mode (Conner and Prahalad (1996))

		Knowledge substitution provides positive net value	
		Yes	No
Higher net value of flexibility provided by	Employment contract	Firm (i)	Firm or market (iv)
	Market Contract renegotiation	Firm or market (ii)	Market (iii)

Model above summarises choices available to the firm to optimally combine resources. In situation (i) supervisor knowledge substitution provides positive effects for value created by firm, coupled with lower costs of flexibility offered by employment contract this leads to unambiguous choice of firm as organisation mode. When the factors are reversed in (iii) market takes over as best mode of combining resources. In situation (ii) is the value of knowledge substitution exceeds value of flexibility offered by the market (lower cost of flexibility in market) then the firm organisation should takes place. Other options are analysed similarly. The central thesis of the article is that the organizational mode through which individuals cooperate affects the knowledge they apply to business activity and the authors conclude that resource-based view is an important steps towards more general theory explaining performance differences between firms.

In his 2008 paper Nelson (2008) revisits firm differences from the viewpoint of comparison with evolutionary biology and argues that research by economists of firm differences and the impact of differences on firms’ survival has been too much focused on formal modelling and that for better insight into the matter more rich and diverse frameworks are required, including more substantial observation into firms qualitative features. This observation has substantial implications in terms of empirical examination of performance variability for the subject papers covered below as well as for the empirical analysis of UK firm data in this dissertation. Nelson (2008) observes that there is preponderant evidence to indicate that almost in all studies there is substantial variability of firms between different industries and that simple model of firm evolution suggesting that profitable firms should expand whilst loss-making contract does not fit the real life data. Nelson (2008) also argues that critical factors behind the differences between the firms and the consequences of these differences are not the same in all industries, again author does not construct any models to prove his reasoning instead following logic of looking at implication of innovation for different firms and industries (e.g. steel vs. shoe production). The author suggests this should be high on the research agenda going forward. An interesting observation made by author is that it appears that substantial variability between firms is caused by firms addressing different customer needs and firms serving different groups of customers (niches) whilst at same time technological flow (technological paradigm in Nelson’s language) is moulding and shaping industrial dynamics by allowing other firms to learn from rival leaders and do something similar themselves. The importance of competition in industries where

technological paradigm is strong is thus less important in generating variability between firms. Author concludes that analysis of the nature and significant of firm variation and industry dynamics is best done in combination of narrative qualitative descriptions of industries and their dynamics in both orientation of data sets and analysis of results. Nelson (2008) paper thus offers a unique and broader perspective into both the modelling approach and interpretation of results then available in other empirical research papers.

In terms of empirical research into what drives variance of firms' profitability a number of studies have been undertaken to address the issue.

Empirical studies

Bain (1951) represents one of the earlier empirical studies of firm performance in relation to industry factors, represented by industry concentration taken as a proxy. In the Bain school of thinking (so called "classical school" in industrial economics) which in turn heavily influenced framework of industry analysis developed by Porter (1980), industry performance is mostly determined by the ability of firms to control competition and industry's competitive structure. Bain (1951) explores the hypothesis that the average profit rate of firms in oligopolistic industries of a high concentration will tend to be significantly larger than that of firms in less concentrated oligopolies or in industries of atomistic structure. The study, using relatively simple statistical tools and descriptions of data concludes that this was probably the case in a sample US manufacturing companies date using performance data from 1936 to 1940. The study revealed substantial dichotomy between profit rates of industries of high concentration (70% concentration measured as value contributed by 8 largest firms) compared to less concentrated industries. The paper also concluded that size of individual firms did not appear to be statistically significantly related to profit rates and neither that other factors mattered for performance or concentration of the industry. Such findings are related to the theoretical concepts developed by Bain in his previous studies and confirmed empirically theoretical constructs. As demonstrated earlier by review of various theories of the firm, classical school of industrial organisation, whilst contributed substantially to the earlier development of the field, does not offer sole explanation for the reasons of firm's existence, neither fully explains variability in firms' performance. The Bain (1951) study is limited in both focusing on manufacturing industries and limited time period (thus influenced by cyclical forces) as well as employing very simple statistical analysis of data. In addition as addressed in later studies (e.g. Gort (1976)) this approach suffers from aggregation of firm performances across industries, entrance and survival bias and potential association between firms' size and performance).

Gort and Singamsetti (1976) were the first to ask whether firms' profit rates "clustered around industry" means. Using several profit rate measures authors found that there is no single-variable relationship between concentration and profit rates, the industry thus exerting only weak effect on the differences in profitability between firms. The results indicate weak role of industry and market in determining firm performance. The additional insight from the study is that profit rates of firms in the more concentrated industries show higher serial correlation, the authors attribute the result to high exit as

well as entry barriers and the difficulties facing concentrated industry firms in redeploying capital tied in specialised resources into more rapidly growing sectors of economy. The authors argue that whilst concentrated industries enjoy stability afforded by limited risks of market erosion from competitive forces they are more vulnerable to structural changes in the economy and composition of demand (such theoretical conclusion can be demonstrated on the Blockbuster example above).

Buzzell et. al (1975) advocated that market share and return on investment are strongly correlated with gains in market share providing additional 5% pre-tax ROI return for each 10% gain in market share. Buzzell provides examples of four factors associated with high market share which contribute to high ROI:

- *Economies of scale* – Larger firms are able to derive economies of scale benefits from their activities across value chain.

- *Experience curve* – The concept pioneered by BCG and related to economies of scale factor above.

- *Market power* – Larger firms able to exercise market power and “administer” pricing power.

- *Quality of management* – It is likely that larger firms will be able to attract better management who in turn are able to positively influence firm performance.

The increase in ROI is associated with the following effects which are analysed in detail in the PIMS study:

- *Increase in gross profit margins* – The purchase to sales ratio for larger firm is lower as they are able to effectively leverage economies of scale in marketing and procurement without associated matching increase in resources required to maintain higher sales volumes.

- *Market leaders are able to offer high quality products and charge higher price* – Market leaders are pursuing product leadership strategies through

continuous and high level investment into R&D. It was shown that larger firms commit on average larger budgets (40%) to R&D when compared to smaller competitors.

In terms of variations between industries PIMS study offers additional interesting insight into importance of market share for various industries:

- *Market share is more important for infrequently purchased products* – The ROI of market leader is about 28 percentage points higher than the ROI of the average small share business. For frequently purchased products (those typically bought at least once a month) ROI differential is accordingly about 10 per cent.
- *Market share is more important for industries where buyers are fragmented* – The ROI differentials are 27 and 19 points accordingly for fragmented and concentrated industries. In concentrated industries buyers dissipate cost advantages by appropriating industry value through exercising bargaining power.

In terms of strategies authors describe typical (build-holding-harvesting) framework which is similar to portfolio analysis tools mentioned above (e.g. BCG matrix). The authors also highlight longer-term nature of market-share and the short-term costs associated with building market share (later examined in more detail by Rumelt and Wensley (1981), Montgomery and Wernerfelt (1991)), with costs of building market share higher for smaller firms compared to market leaders.

The findings from PIMS study are both interesting and in use today by management of companies and practitioners of strategy. It appears that despite authors outlining the risks of market share building strategy in their original studies these were sometimes ignored in practice by management which could be attributed to difficulties in measurement of benefits of higher market share over longer term. In addition Rumelt and Wensley (1981) argue that benefits from increased market share should be fully incorporated into relevant costs (e.g. marketing) and thus share-building should not be an exercise in itself. The criticism of portfolio analysis tools are coming mostly from resource-based view not only on the net value of market share benefits as above but also on other aspects of recommendations ensuing from the framework. Thus Prahalad and Hamel (1990) show that excessive focus on market and competitive positions of SBUs can have detrimental effects on corporations over long term when strategic resources and competencies are lost through divestment of market positions and products as prescribed by portfolio analysis models (e.g. complete loss of competitive positions by US manufacturers in TV area). In addition other authors (Gadiesh and Gilbert (1998)) argue that new set of imperatives is called for focusing on share of profits instead of market share and revenues by introducing

concept of profit-pool enabling companies to look at their industries, firms and product through a completely different lens to formulate strategy by overturning old assumptions.

Rumelt and Wensley (1981) found that market share appears to have no intrinsic value. The authors argued that even if market share was an asset which had value, they would expect firms to be paying for gains in share, instead the study found that those firms which are gaining market shares most rapidly are also experiencing largest simultaneous increases in profitability. Such result is in conflict with portfolio analysis positioning models and PIMS study, however could be simply explained within resource-based model as efficiencies obtained through utilisation of better resources drive market share and profitability at the same time.

Montgomery A., Wernerfelt B. (1991) explored sources of value creation in the U.S. brewing industry between 1969 and 1979 by looking at whether positive association exists between market share building strategies as prescribed by popular portfolio analysis models and findings from PIMS study. In order to address drawbacks of previously used models (Rumelt and Wensley (1981)), in particular use of accounting measures of return, the fact that benefits from gaining market share are realised over longer term, the authors advocate use of capital market measures by using variation of CAPM model. Authors performed analysis of value decomposition in the US brewing industry in order to control for industry resource configuration which did not change during period of time under review. The previous studies did not control for change in industry resource configuration, thus it could be argued correlation observed between returns of individual firms and their market shares could have been driven by other factors arising out of change in resource configuration. The study concluded that after controlling the factors above: 1) On average gains in market share were associated with destruction rather than creation of value. 2) A portion of the industry component came from excessive competition rather than collision. The results of the study are thus very different from previous studies (Buzzell (1975)) and Bain (1951)). The study also found small part of individual firm returns explained by industry (15%-20%) in line with other studies like Schmalensee's (1985).

Prescott et. al (1998) follow a different approach by analyzing impact of market share on performance across taxonomy of homogeneous environments. The authors found that 1) association between market share and performance is context-specific; 2) both direct and spurious relationship exists and their relative strength vary across different contexts 3) the validity of market-share as predictor of performance is context specific. Of the 7 environments studied in 3 the effect was mainly direct, whilst in the other 4 it was predominantly spurious. In addition in 3 environments where direct effect was dominating there was still substantial spurious effect. Given the findings, authors advocate careful pursuit of market share as a goal.

Ravenscraft (1983) examined structure-profit relationship using disaggregated data at the line-of-business. The results of the study found the effect of market share on performance positive and significant, whilst the coefficient of concentration was negative and significant. Ravenscraft interpreted his results as supporting the argument that concentration variable does not appear to be a valid proxy for the ability to collude. The study also identified positive effects on performance of advertising and assets intensity over certain levels of market share (4.4% and 9.5% accordingly) together with negative effect from R&D spend. The positive association between performance and advertising/assets intensity may reflect in turn higher product quality and lower unit costs. The study concludes that a number of unresolved questions remain which the use of static data analysis can not illuminate.

Schmalensee (1985) approached study of profitability variance in a novel and fundamentally different way to previous studies. The author argues that one of the reasons conventional measures perform poorly in cross-sectional studies (in particular concentration variables) is because they are imperfect measure of industry structure. The study found no support either for the existence of firm effects, or for the importance of market share effects (weak effects found). Industry effects exist, are important (at least 75% of the variance of industry rates of return on assets are explained by the industry and 20% of the variance in business unit returns is similarly can be attributed to industry) and negatively correlated with concentration. The result of the study thus support classical focus on the industry-level analysis and downplay the importance of revisionist schools (resource-based, managerial approach). At the same way authors cautions that the results can not be interpreted as an uncritical return to cross-section analysis in particular as looking at one year data ignores the cyclical factors affecting different industries and firms. It is also important to recognise that 80 per cent of the variance in business unit profitability is unrelated to industry of share effects. While industry difference matter, they are clearly not all that matters according to author. Finally whilst the study was novel in that of focusing on relative importance of market share and concluded that market share effect was relatively insignificant compared to industry when used to explain firms' profitability, the coefficient of 0.2304 attributed to market share in regression is still significant to warrant attention. It is worth noticing that whilst coefficient is still significant it appears considerably lower to market share sensitivity of ROI (in the regions of 0.5) identified in PIMS studies. Schmalensee's study was both innovative and sophisticated to provide additional insight into empirical performance of firms both in comparison with previous studies and different theoretical approaches as advocated by classical and revisionist approaches.

Cubbin, J. and Geroski, P. (1987) reviewed previous approaches to analysing performance variability, including both noting limitations of explicit structural models at statistical level and ingenuity of Schmalensee's (1985) approach described above. The authors adopt a different explicitly dynamic approach applied to time series data. This study represents particular interest due to both

difference in approach and the fact that it was applied to UK firms data, as opposed to US company studies undertaken in all other research. Whilst it is possible to expect similar performance of both industry and firms in the UK compared to the US, it is important to see whether UK offers modifications of industry and firms' behaviour, in particular the importance of industry effects in the UK is explicitly addressed by the study. The study revealed that only 55% of firms exhibited at least some dynamic communality with rivals in the same industry and very few, if any, firms appeared capable of being subsumed into "average" or "representative firm" as espoused by Porter's "shared asset" theories. The study also revealed that entry forces appeared to be more strong than mobility forces meaning that many firms were able to occupy market niches better protected than those on average in their industry. This has implications for relative strength of "entry" versus "mobility" barriers. The additional evidence arising from the study is that returns are not equalised across all firms and sectors even in the long run. Whilst two thirds of firms converged towards common profitability level, a solid core of firms was able to maintain some independence from market forces more or less indefinitely. Market power and industry structure variables are thus insufficient to describe industry dynamics, as certain firms enjoy market power more and for much longer than others.

Hansen and Wernerfelt (1989) integrated empirical study of effects predicted by both economic and organizational paradigms. Using representative models from each paradigm separately and then in combination authors founds that both sets of factors are significant in explaining variability of firms' performance. The additional substantial findings were that the two effects were in approximation independent from each other with organizational factors explaining (37.78%) of variation in performance, which is twice compared with industry (18.50%). In terms of methodological approach the authors used a combination of factors normally identified in relevant paradigm models, including industry profitability as benchmark for industry structure, market share, assets and two variables representing "organizational climate". The authors conclude that both competitive positioning in marketplace and building firm capabilities for competitive advantage are important, however given relative importance of explanatory factors it is the building of an effective, directed, human organization in the selected industries which is critical.

Bowman and Helfat (2001) addressed the corporate effect issue in empirical examination of variability of returns. Following review of corporate strategy theories authors argue that the size of estimated effects other than corporate effect do not provide a standard for assessing the performance of corporate strategy. The authors then reviewed empirical studies to make several observations about the corporate effect: 1) The inclusions of single-business firms masks corporate effect in multiple-business firms, the higher the ratio of single-business firms the lower observed corporate effect. 2) Broad definitions of industries and businesses produce lower estimates of corporate effect. 3) Analysis of variance produces upper-bounds estimates of corporate effect. 4) Studies which do not include

covariance between corporate effect and time/industry do not fully account for influence of corporate strategy on profitability. The authors conclude that contrary to revisionist view, variance decomposition studies suggest that corporate strategy matters.

Rumelt (1991) further developed Schmalensee's (1985) approach by addressing the difference between stable and fluctuating effects and reached conclusions very different from Schmalensee. The study concluded that stable industry effects are small (8.28% of the variance of business unit returns and only about 40% per cent of the dispersion in industry returns is due to stable industry effects) whilst business effects are large and stable. Business unit effects accounted for 46 per cent of the variance in business unit profitability. Business units differed from one another within industries a great deal more than industries differed from one another. The study also found that 7.84% of variance was explained by the industry-year effect. The author concluded that: 1) there are significant business unit effects that strongly outweigh industry and corporate membership as predictors of profitability. 2) Corporate effects are not important in explaining the dispersion of observed rates of return among business units (i.e. there is no "synergy").

Roquebert et al.(1996) performed evaluation of relative degree of variance in return of assets accounted for by industry, corporate and SBU effects whilst controlling for the business cycle and the interacting between business cycle and industry. The study mostly confirmed Rumelt (1991) results whilst also suggesting the existence of non-trivial corporate effect (17.9%). The authors explained other differences between relative effects of firm and industry compared to Rumelt's (1991) study by the more new data set and also by difference in data structure itself. The authors concluded that certainly strategic management theory has a significant role to play. The authors also found support for other conclusions in Rumelt's (1991) study, including insignificant industry effects (10% vs. 8% in Rumelt's study), the fact that industries are heterogeneous and firms differ from each other a great deal more than industries differ from each other, and that SBU ROA is appropriate unit of analysis instead of industry averages. The authors also found insignificant impact of size on ROA, whilst noting the importance of corporate effect (0%-20%), similar to Bowman and Helfat's (2001) study above noting negative correlation between diversification and corporate effect. This is broadly in line with disillusion with popularity of diversification after 1980s both in academic research and among managers.

Porter M. and McGahan, A. (1997) revisited the issue of relevant contribution to performance by industry, year and business specific effects. The authors found that industry, corporate-parent, and business specific effects are related in complex ways. Study results indicate that year, industry, corporate parent and business specific effects accounted for 2, 19, 4 and 32 per cent, respectively, of the aggregate variance in profitability. The industry effect is thus more powerful than in Rumelt's (1991) study. The study also provides additional insight on factor contribution across different industries. Industry accounts for smaller portion of

variance in manufacturing, but a larger portion in lodging/entertainment, services, wholesale/retail trade and transportation. The authors concluded that: 1) Industry directly accounted for 19% of aggregate variation in business specific profits, and 36% per cent of explained variation. 2) Industry influenced the effect of the corporate parent on business specific profitability. 3) The absolute and relative influence of industry, corporate parent and business specific effects differed substantially across broad economic sectors in ways which suggest characteristic differences in their industry structural context. 4) Industry effects were more persistent over time than business specific or corporate parent effects, which is consistent with the view that industry structure changes more slowly.

Mauri, M. and Michaels, M. (1998) addressed complementarity issue between economic and resource-based views. Whilst firms differ in possession of unique valuable resources enabling them to deploy effectively strategies to obtain sustainable competitive advantage the opposing industry forces cause convergence over time as observable marketing campaigns and technologies are duplicated. The findings from the study confirmed that most variability was caused by firm-specific factors whilst industry specific factors accounted for majority of variability in R&D and marketing strategies. The findings thus supported the view that firms develop homogeneous responses to formulation of marketing strategies and investing into R&D. The firms thus imitate easily observable variables and factors in order to close competitive gaps in these areas. Together firm and industry account for between 74 and 94 in of the total variance in strategy variables pointing to pattern of strategy. The findings support Rumelt's (1991) results that unique resource endowments are primary drivers of performance. The authors advocated that the task of general management is to adjust and renew firm resources as time, competition and change erode their value (Rumelt (1987)). The researches on the other side should focus on differences and not similarities in resources, whilst only analyzing "finer grain" resources can add value.

Hawawini et al. (2002) continued research into relative contribution of factors to the variability of firm performance using expanded data set and modified methodology. The authors also analyzed variability by using economic value-added factors compared to previously widespread use of accounting ratios. The authors concluded that similar to previous studies firm effects dominated long-term performance irrespective of whether performance is measured by EP/CE, TMV/CE or ROA. The consistent results demonstrated between use of EVA indicators and ROA is encouraging given significant previous body of research using only accounting measures. Stable firm effects explained considerably more variance in the dependent variable than total industry effects, which are the sum of the stable and transient components. Total industry effects for EP/CE, TMV/CE and ROA were 10.7 percent, 14.3 percent and 11.2 percent (the sum of industry and industry-year effects). In comparison, corresponding figures for stable firm effects were 27.1 percent, 32.5 percent and 35.8 percent. The dominance of firm effects was even more pronounced when authors compared

stable firm-specific effects with stable industry effects in the case of EP/CE and ROA, when stable firm effects dominated stable industry effects by a factor of more than four, while in the case of TMV/CE the amount of variance explained by stable firm effects was approximately three times more than that of stable industry effects.

The authors also provided additional insight into variability of firm performance by looking into whether outliers in both value-creators and value-destroyers had a substantial effect on the variability of performance. It was demonstrated that only a few firms that captured or destroyed a large part of industry's value dominated intra-industry and firm effects.

In a sample of firms where outliers were excluded when performance is measured with TMV/CE, overall industry effect (the sum of stable and transient industry effects) explained 35.2 percent in variation compared to only 17.0 percent for firm effects. In the case of EP/CE it was 18.2 percent for industry effects vs. 17.6 for firm effects and for ROA it was 20.1 per cent against 16.7 percent. In general, for a majority of the industry's firms, when the industry outliers (leaders and losers) were discarded, industry effects seemed to dominate firm effects in explaining the variations in performance.

The findings indicated that a significant proportion of the absolute estimates of the variance of firm-specific factors in the study was due to the presence of a few firms that consistently and substantially deviated from the rest of the industry. The implication is that for leaders and losers firm factors matter more than industry factors. Contrary to the vast majority of other firms, i.e. for firms that are neither industry leaders nor losers, the industry effect turned out to be more important for performance than firm-specific factors.

A possible explanation of this phenomenon is that superior (or poor) management leads to superior (or poor) firm performance irrespective of industry structure. In other words, industry structure matters only for firms that do not manage to be the leader or the loser, i.e. for firms with average managerial capabilities and performance.

4 The research methodology

The research methodology consisted broadly from application of both theoretical and empirical tools covered in Section 3 of this dissertation. In addition to statistical examination of empirical data more rigorous model and approach used by Schmalensee (1985) and later developed by Rumelt (1991) and other authors were used.

The benefits of methodology originally used by authors above in application to research into variability of performance and relevant factors as applied to US firm data are primarily deriving from limited assumptions postulated about the underlying processes and data sets used in the research. This is in contrast to regression factor analysis models where various assumptions should be made about behavior of industries and firms. Whilst regression factor analysis models can provide additional insight into values of coefficients attributed to different factors driving variability of performance both review of theoretical research and empirical examinations indicate difficulties involved in using regression analysis tools.

From the theoretical perspective, identification of specific factors driving performance across various industries and population of firms is very difficult if not impossible task given current state of knowledge on the subject. Multiple studies previously undertaken using proxies for industry concentration, market shares etc did not reach conclusive results. Indeed in his novel study Schmalensee (1985) noted that “we have very imperfect measures of the classic dimensions of market structure and basic conditions” and cited this as a reason for poor or perverse performance of conventional market-level variables. Identification of specific factors is thus difficult even in establishing industry impact on firm performance even leaving aside resource-based models and arguments. Resource-based arguments offer additional complexity dimension to the problem at hand, from lack of consistent factor set at the theoretical level to practical issues at identifying and measuring specific factors in empirical analysis.

Given above frameworks adopted initially by Schmalensee (1985) and later by Rumelt (1991) were applied in the empirical study of data in this dissertation. The models were adapted and modified to both take account of empirical results in studies quoted earlier as well as allow for data availability for this project. The study of data was undertaken by using analysis of variance framework which allowed to focus directly on existence and importance of year, industry, industry-year and firm effects without sacrificing reality by imposing various assumptions. Detailed description of calculations required to obtain results in the analysis of variance framework can be found for example in Rumelt (1991) paper.

In terms of data, review of the literature above highlighted use of different data sets by different authors. In addition more recent papers took advantage of availability of more detailed data over longer period of time. At the same time it

was considered that balance was required in terms of number of firms in observation as well as time period of observation. Whilst Rumelt (1991) correctly noted that use of static data is likely to be affected by impact of economic cycle on specific industries, later studies like Porter and McGahan (1997) mostly confirmed conclusions on relative strength of industry vs. firm effects achieved by Schmalensee (1985) whilst covering substantially longer period of time compared to Rumelt's (1991) study. It should also be noted better availability of US firm data compared to other countries including UK using publicly available information as well as sources available as part of Warwick MBA resources.

Given the above, for the purposes of this study the financial data of constituents of FTSE 100 index over 5-years as available from Thomson One Banker was used. As indicated in other studies, whilst critique over use of accounting data is valid on theoretical grounds, the results from other studies using economic value-added framework (EVA) which are more directly linked to maximization of shareholder wealth, indicated consistency between results achieved using accounting ratios when compared to use of EVA factors. In terms of accounting ratios, return on assets (ROA) as reported by Thomson One Banker was used offering consistency to previous studies (majority of studies used ROA as a performance measure) as well as measurement consistency over different firms and industries.

The model used was a variation of model used in Rumelt (1991) study.

$$r_{ikt} = \mu + \alpha_i + \gamma_t + \delta_{it} + \varphi_{ik} + \varepsilon_{ikt}$$

where r_{ikt} return on assets as reported by Thomson One Banker.

α_i – industry effects

γ_t – year effects

δ_{it} и φ_{ik} -industry year interaction effect and business unit effect accordingly

ε_{ikt} –random disturbances

In terms of variation from the original Rumelt (1991) model they were main differences:

- 1) In terms of availability of data no split of performance data was available in terms of segments etc. Thus overall firm data was used including firm specific ROA etc.
- 2) The corporate effect modeled by Rumelt was explicitly suppressed in the model above. This was both due driven by availability of data in 1) above as well as primary objective of determining existence and importance of industry

and firm specific factors causing variability of performance. Majority of empirical research above concluded on insignificance of corporate effects, with Rumelt’s study finding only “astonishingly small” effects.

Similar to Rumelt (1991) the terms γ_t – year effects and δ_{it} industry year interaction effect were added to the model to account for overall business cycle and the differential impact of business cycle on various industries. It should be noted that period of time under observation covers financial accounts from financial year-end 2009 going back 5 years and thus covered both rising part of the business cycle as well as significant drop in output due to credit crisis and recession later. From statistical characteristics of the data set whilst majority of industries reflected business cycle, some industries like financials, oil and real estate experienced even more substantial falls. It was thus important to model economic cycle effect at overall level as well as its effect on various industries.

Return on assets – data set (T = 2009, T-4 = 2005)

	T	T-1	T-2	T-3	T-4	ROA
Basic Materials	6.90	9.50	14.85	18.38	14.28	11.98
Consumer Goods	8.99	9.15	12.43	12.21	12.28	11.01
Consumer Services	8.72	7.16	11.85	10.50	9.34	9.12
Financials	2.72	0.36	3.70	3.20	3.45	2.67
Health Care	13.67	10.21	12.03	18.08	12.61	13.32
Industrials	6.70	6.45	13.90	9.61	7.72	8.88
Oil & Gas	5.50	9.53	19.98	8.98	10.28	9.90
REIT	4.89	-26.61	-1.38	19.58	10.92	1.48
Technology	7.85	7.85	6.69	7.23	5.58	7.04
Telecommunications	7.17	7.18	7.52	7.24	0.55	5.93
Utilities	6.53	3.17	9.89	6.23	8.60	6.89
Average	7.24	4.00	10.13	11.02	8.69	8.02

Variability of return on assets – data set (T = 2009, T-4 = 2005)

	T	T-1	T-2	T-3	T-4	ROA	Deviation
Basic Materials	58%	79%	124%	153%	119%	100%	96%
Consumer Goods	82%	83%	113%	111%	111%	100%	31%
Consumer Services	96%	78%	130%	115%	102%	100%	51%
Financials	102%	13%	139%	120%	129%	100%	125%
Health Care	103%	77%	90%	136%	95%	100%	59%
Industrials	75%	73%	157%	108%	87%	100%	84%
Oil & Gas	56%	96%	202%	91%	104%	100%	146%
REIT	330%	-1799%	-93%	1324%	738%	100%	3123%

Technology	111%	111%	95%	103%	79%	100%	32%
Telecommunications	121%	121%	127%	122%	9%	100%	117%
Utilities	95%	46%	144%	91%	125%	100%	98%

The COV (analysis of variance) method used in this empirical analysis adopts assumption that all effects (variances of α_i γ_t δ_{it} ϕ_{ik} ϵ_{ikt} independent variables set) are random disturbances, drawn independently from distribution with zero mean and unknown variance). The real advantage and substance of such model is that the differences among effects are “natural” whatever their source and have not been artificially constrained or distorted by model design.

The data set contained 5-year financial results of FTSE 100 constituent firms.

5 The results

This section presents results from statistical analysis of empirical data as well as estimates of relative factors driving performance variability using model described in Section 4.

Statistical analysis of empirical data

In terms of statistical characteristics of the data set the graph below describes performance of various industries over 5-year time period in comparison with the average performance of all constituents of FTSE-100 index. Performance measure was taken as ROA (return on assets) as calculated by Thomson One Banker database. Such measure of performance was used to ensure consistency with both the previous research as well as for consistent comparison of statistical results with results from the model.

ROA by industry, FTSE 100 index constituents

Graph above provides descriptive summary of statistical analysis of performance data for industry components of FTSE-100 index. The following observations are made which are both elaborated on and explained in Section 6 of the dissertation:

- The impact of economic cycle on all industries. In particular significant variations are noted between exposure to business cycle, in particular dramatic underperformance of financials and real estate even when compared to high-value beta sectors. This is in line with what is normally expected of high-beta sectors, accentuated by additional significant impact of this particular economic cycle, both the reasons and effects of which are closely linked to real estate and mortgage industries. Significant collapse of real estate assets prices across the globe, but more so in particular in countries including US and UK, has both impacted and was affected by the non-performing loans and write-offs in the

banking sector, including effective nationalization of participants more exposed to the property sector (Northern Rock and RBS).

Additionally dispersion of ROA returns by sector was calculated and analyzed which is a useful metric in the analysis of performance variability factors examined in more detail in Section 6. The average dispersion of ROA across all industries was 13.52%.

Performance variability – analysis of factors

COV results developed from model equation

Industry	12.1	14.49%
Year	4.6	5.48%
Industry-year	8.3	9.89%
Firm	15.1	18.07%
Error	43.6	52.07%
Total	83.8	100.00%

Table above provides estimates of model equation using COV method, variability of different factors is presented in absolute values as well as in normalized form.

Results indicate that 48% per cent of the total variance in firm performance is explained by the model. The error not explained by model is 52.07%. This is broadly in line with other studies, e.g. with Porter and McGahan (1997) reporting errors ranging from 80.41% in original Schmalensee (1985) study to 48.40% in Porter and McGahan (1997) which is close to error in this study. As noted by authors the error

arises because profits are subject to shocks, a portion of which may be carried from one year to the next.

6 Discussion of results

This section covers in detail discussion of results obtained from statistical analysis and results from application of the model to establish existence and relative contribution of performance variability factors.

Statistical examination of performance data

The average ROA of all firms was 8.02%. The population of all firms, as represented by FTSE-100 index, experienced substantial variation in returns over the last 5-years with ROA ranging from 11.02% for 2006 to 4% for 2008. The period of the observation is very interesting due to unparalleled economic contraction which unfolded in 2008 following credit crisis.

The FTSE 100 index of leading firms is the most observed market performance metric in the UK and also globally to benchmark performance of UK stock market. FTSE 100 broadly reflected financial performance of constituent firms as expressed by ROA with index reaching highest 6,721.60 point on 1st Nov 07 and consequently falling to the lowest point of 3,645.87 on 5th March 2009 – a drop of 46%. The market then started to gradually recover before another sharp correction from mid-April to the end of

June (16% index drop) and is currently (Nov 2010) at 5,750, 14% from its peak 3 years ago.

This is in line with financial performance, forward looking stock market started to fall before results of financial performance for the full 2007 year in comparison with 2006 were released. Additional falls of both ROA and FTSE 100 in 2008 were followed by recovery in 2009.

In terms of index component performance perhaps the more illuminating analysis is performed by looking at individual industries.

1) Basic materials:

This part of FTSE 100 index predominantly represents mining companies.

Mining industry exhibited good returns despite onset of global economic crisis, which is mostly attributed to strong performance of commodity prices, in particular gold and silver, over the last 5 years with prices reaching highest levels recently. Antofagasta, BHP Billiton and Fresnillo were the highest performers in terms of ROA, all exhibiting returns over 20% substantially in excess of both average FTSE 100 and average industry return (8% and 11.98% accordingly). This was in turn reflected in stock market performance with stocks returning 335%, 170% and 165% accordingly over 5-year period. The industry ROA laggards accordingly delivered 7.56% (Lonmin) and 536% (Randgold). The stock market outlier performance of Randgold can thus not be explained by the low ROA factor. Median firm Anglo American delivered 15.03% ROIC and 48.33% shareholder return. Rio Tinto delivered 18.80% ROIC and 75.55% shareholder return.

From the analysis of dispersion majority of returns concentrated in the 5%-20% performance band with one outlier represented by African Barrick Gold. The overall dispersion of returns was 24.91%, which is significantly in excess of average across industries of 13.52%.

The findings for mining industry are generally in line with previous literature, for example McGahan and Porter (1997) reported strong industry effects in mining with industry effects accounting for 39.50 percent compared to 29.35 of variation explained by individual firms. Given improved economics of industry due to positive factors on the supply side (lack of new supplies due to neglect of mining during dot com era, substantial lags in creating new capacity, substantial industry barriers) as well as improved pricing industry benefited substantially which was reflected both in ROA and stock market performance, with industry leaders exhibiting substantial outperformance despite onset of economic crisis. Following Hawawini et al. (2002) it can be concluded that industry performance benefited average mining company, whilst addition industry leaders additionally benefited from through exploitation of their core competencies for competitive advantage.

2) Consumer goods:

The industry consists of large consumer goods companies producing and selling fashion, household, alcohol and tobacco products. As expected, the industry exhibited good financial performance with lowest volatility across all sectors despite the economic crisis. Reckitt Benckiser, household products company, led the performance in terms of ROA, which was in turn reflected in both excellent return on invested capital (ROIC) and stock performance (96% over 5 years), whilst exhibiting low volatility (beta of 0.37).

Reckitt-Benkiser, profitability ratios

PROFITABILITY	12/31/09	12/31/08	12/31/07	12/31/06	12/31/05
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Return On Assets	16.22	15.72	17.15	14.71	17.14
Return On Invested Capital	31.71	30.13	34.00	29.37	35.31

The industry exhibited lower dispersion (11.01%) compared to average across sectors (13.52%). From analysis of industry returns it is apparent that Reckit-Benkiser enjoys industry leader advantages, which manifested themselves in both ROA substantially higher (almost full 3% over next best return by Diageo) complemented by additional advantages to achieve substantially higher ROIC (5%+ advantages) without taking additional risk (beta of 0.37 compared to 0.47 for BAT below and 0.67 for 0.57 for Diageo). Reckit-Benkiser (RB) is thus truly “excellent” firm (following Peters and Waterman (1982) terminology) consistently providing returns in excess of both industry and the market. In terms of resource-based school additional examination of RB resource-position and time-based flow is thus merited, but not covered in this dissertation given its scope and focus.

Following Hawawini et al. (2002) it is interesting to see whether for average firms performance was substantially below that one of RB.

British American Tobacco, profitability ratios (beta 0.47)

PROFITABILITY	12/31/09	12/31/08	12/31/07	12/31/06	12/31/05
Return On Assets	11.71	12.35	13.33	12.02	11.16
Return On Invested Capital	16.51	17.10	17.54	15.88	14.76

Unilever, profitability ratios (beta 0.67)

PROFITABILITY	12/31/09	12/31/08	12/31/07	12/31/06
Return On Assets	9.87	13.82	11.45	13.99
Return On Invested Capital	16.13	22.66	19.55	24.99

Whilst both ROA and ROE for British American Tobacco and Unilever were substantially below that of Reckit-Benkiser’s, the relevant stock returns were 85% and 51%. Whilst BAT returns were not substantially lower than those of RB it could be argued that tobacco stock are less representative in that regard than that of Unilever (given well know fact that tobacco stocks consistently deliver excellent shareholder returns, concentrated nature of the tobacco industry and nature of the product for which consumers historically paid higher prices due to increase in taxation), with RB delivering extra 45% shareholder return over the last 5 years (dividends excluded in both cases).

Finally comparison with the “laggard” sector firms provides an interesting additional insight between the link between financial performance and stock market performance. Whilst accounting measures of profitability of both Sabmiller and Imperial Tobacco were substantially less than those of Reckit-Benkiser’s both stocks have outperformed RB returning 105% for Sabmiller and 306% for Imperial Tobacco accordingly. It is not clear whether such differences were caused by distortions caused over the use by accounting

measures as opposed to economic-value measures, some additional factors contributing to stock outperformance in the absence of high ROA or a combination of two reasons. Unfortunately Hawawini et al. (2002) does not provide industry by industry analysis over use of economic-value added measures as compared to accounting measures to provide additional insight whether consumer goods industry is better examined with the use of EVA-like measurers due to potential distortions cause by non-recording of value of brands on companies' balance sheets.

Sabmiller, profitability ratios (beta 1.01)

PROFITABILITY	03/31/10	03/31/09	03/31/08	03/31/07	03/31/06
Return On Assets	5.98	7.34	7.64	7.26	8.08
Return On Invested Capital	7.38	9.13	9.76	9.26	10.19

Imperial Tobacco, profitability ratios (beta 0.52)

PROFITABILITY	09/30/09	09/30/08	09/30/07	09/30/06	09/30/05
Return On Assets	3.94	4.89	13.60	14.57	11.16
Return On Invested Capital	6.39	7.42	19.98	22.60	18.28

3) Consumer services:

The industry consists of a selection of large companies aggregated into this group, compared to other industries representing more variability due to member firms coming from diverse sectors represented by publishing, hotels, retail, travel and advertising. Intra-industry comparisons are thus arguable less useful compared to other industries.

Given diverse nature of the “industry” (same terminology is used here whilst arguably this is less applicable in everyday’s use of the word), it is perhaps not surprising that the largest dispersion of returns was observed, from -0.53% for TUI Travel to 29.86% for Reed Elsevier – overall 30.39% dispersion compared with average of 13.52% across industries.

Again similar to mining and consumer goods weak link was observed between industry leading position and stock market performance with Reed Elsevier actually destroying shareholder wealth over 5-year period of time (dividends excluded) – the negative return of 9.56%. This was despite ROIC in excess of 30% (30.75%).

Reed Elsevier, profitability ratios (beta 0.55)

PROFITABILITY	12/31/09	12/31/08	12/31/07	12/31/06	12/31/05
Return On Assets	27.05	22.96	46.67	29.36	23.28
Return On Invested Capital	27.46	23.26	47.85	30.74	24.45

In comparison median-firms Tesco and Carnival delivered 36.54% and -19.38% whilst publishing peer Pearson 44.17% returned at substantially lower ROA and ROIC ratios.

Pearson, profitability ratios (beta 0.77)

PROFITABILITY	12/31/09	12/31/08	12/31/07	12/31/06	12/31/05
Return On Assets	5.26	4.43	4.90	7.97	10.29
Return On Invested Capital	6.96	5.68	6.21	10.11	13.20

TUI travel, the lowest performer in terms of ROA delivered negative 27.22% shareholder return over 5 years.

TUI travel, profitability ratios (beta 0.87)

PROFITABILITY	09/30/09	09/30/08
Return On Assets	0.42	-1.48
Return On Invested Capital	1.04	-3.18

4) Financials:

The industry exhibited above average (16.79%) dispersion of returns, however this was mostly due to an outlier - Admiral Group. If Admiral Group is excluded industry exhibits less than average dispersion of 6.81%. Whilst Admiral Group delivered excellent ROIC (52.02%) and shareholder return of 229.03%, the performance of median firms varied – Investec delivered 7.28% whilst Standard Chartered shares increased by 50% over the last 5 years. The lowest ROA firm ICAP delivered 26.81% whilst Royal Bank of Scotland is currently trading at 6.4% of its value 5 years ago – destroying over 94.6% of shareholder wealth during this period of time.

Admiral Group, profitability ratios (beta 0.6)

PROFITABILITY	12/31/09	12/31/08	12/31/07	12/31/06	12/31/05
Return On Assets	17.36	18.34	18.03	16.22	15.46
Return On Invested Capital	54.39	56.44	55.67	48.95	44.66

5) Healthcare:

The industry exhibited above average (16.55%) variability of returns. Industry peers have limited representation as other major healthcare companies are quoted on other stock exchanges (US, Switzerland etc). Of the two most comparable, Glaxosmithkline PLC and Astrazeneca had comparable beta-values and profitability ratios (GSK slightly higher). GSK returned -13.27% whilst Astrazeneca achieved 17.71% shareholder return over 5 years – substantial over performance especially in light of lower financial ratios. Similar to consumer goods industry the question remains over validity of use of accounting ratios in the healthcare industry, given the value of pharmaceutical companies’ brands and patents.

Glaxosmithkline, profitability ratios (beta 0.5)

PROFITABILITY	12/31/09	12/31/08	12/31/07	12/31/06	12/31/05
Return On Assets	15.81	15.85	21.14	23.28	21.84
Return On Invested Capital	23.67	23.06	31.01	38.62	38.64

Astrazeneca, profitability ratios (beta 0.53)

PROFITABILITY	12/31/09	12/31/08	12/31/07	12/31/06	12/31/05
Return On Assets	15.61	13.08	15.50	23.04	19.74
Return On Invested Capital	25.92	20.93	25.11	38.21	31.03

6) Industrials:

Industrials exhibited return in line with average (13.97%) variability of returns. Smith Group and Intertek were industry leaders with Smith Group exhibiting higher ROA and ROIC ratios (ROIC: 26.72% and 23.22% accordingly).

Smith Group, profitability ratios (beta 0.74)

PROFITABILITY	07/31/09	07/31/08	07/31/07	08/05/06	07/31/05
Return On Assets	10.60	10.04	55.75	0.94	7.84
Return On Invested Capital	17.01	15.84	86.69	1.44	12.62

Intertek Group, profitability ratios (beta 0.94)

PROFITABILITY	12/31/09	12/31/08	12/31/07	12/31/06	12/31/05
Return On Assets	13.47	13.58	16.14	17.27	18.12
Return On Invested Capital	18.68	19.13	23.53	26.09	28.65

Smith Group and Intertek Group produced 13.11% and 141.21% stock returns accordingly again pointing to substantial differences in stock performance for reasons other than difference in accounting ratios. Median firms Cobham and Bunzl produced 21.27% and 21.21% accordingly whilst ROA laggard GKN reduced shareholder wealth by 34.34%.

7) Oil & Gas:

Oil & Gas had 16.21% dispersion of returns which is higher than average. The industry ROA leaders BG Group and Cairn Energy exhibited ROIC ratios of 21.32% and 127.83% accordingly (with Cairn Energy ROIC fluctuated significantly being smaller exploration company). The shareholder return was 115.41% for BG Group and 90.99% for Cairn.

BG Group, profitability ratios (beta 0.67)

PROFITABILITY	12/31/09	12/31/08	12/31/07	12/31/06	12/31/05
Return On Assets	8.73	15.93	12.99	15.10	15.81
Return On Invested Capital	13.41	26.30	20.82	22.81	23.27

Cairn Energy, profitability ratios (beta 1.26)

PROFITABILITY	12/31/09	12/31/08	12/31/07	12/31/06	12/31/05
Return On Assets	0.39	10.13	69.85	-5.11	7.68
Return On Invested Capital	0.48	13.12	112.64	-9.16	10.75

ROA and shareholder returns in oil industry, 2005-2009

Company	ROA	Return
Essar Energy PLC	0.38	31.19%
Tullow Oil PLC	7.94	361.87%
BP PLC	9.37	-34.05%
Amec PLC	9.91	209.17%
Royal Dutch Shell PLC	9.95	9.69%
Petrofac Limited	11.35	563.15%
BG Group PLC	13.71	115.41%
Cairn Energy PLC	16.59	90.99%

The ROA and shareholder return for 5-years in oil industry are indicated in the table above. There is very substantial variation in shareholder return factors which can hardly be explained by industry or difference in ROA. In terms of resource-based view an explanation offered by Barney (1991) can be applied to oil & gas industry, namely:

- 1) In general it is not possible to acquire resource advantages through competitive markets.
- 2) Firms seeking to obtain above normal returns must be consistently better informed about value of these resources by having more accurate expectations. As an alternative firms could be lucky by inadvertently

acquiring and deploying resources, the benefits of which later turn out to exceed acquisition costs.

Whilst significant element of chance is present in oil exploration given both the high costs of drilling and other factors, it could be argued that some firms like Cairn were able to acquire resource advantages through better expectations (licenses acquired by Cairn in India were sold by Shell at relatively low cost compared to major oil find).

8) REITs:

Land Securities Group, profitability ratios (beta 1.17)

PROFITABILITY	03/31/10	03/31/09	03/31/08	03/31/07	03/31/06
Return On Assets	12.74	-35.61	-3.02	22.92	14.76
Return On Invested Capital	13.66	-39.14	-3.46	27.73	18.44

Industry leading firm, Land Securities Group ROIC was only 3.45% with shareholder return of 58.16% over 5 year time period reflecting credit crisis and substantial fall in values of real estate. On the contrary, ROA laggard Capital Shopping Centers Group delivered slightly positive return of 1.69% (ROIC 0.74%).

9) Technology:

Technology sector has very limited representation in FTSE 100 as majority of technology companies are quoted in US or elsewhere. ROA dispersion was lowest across all sectors with ROA ranging from 5.3% to 8.68%. The Sage Group had ROIC of 11.94% (beta of 0.69) whilst ARM Holding's ROIC was only 5.79%. The sector exhibited diverging returns with Sage returning 10.87% and ARM Holding 217.11%. A comment similar to that for consumer services is appropriate here in that technology is a collective name to aggregate firms under common name here whilst arguable accounting software and semiconductor industries belong to different sectors driven by completely difference set of both industry fundamentals and core competencies.

10) Telecommunications:

Vodafone exhibited negative ROIC of 0.57% over 5-years however given acquisitive nature of company during last decade and significant write-offs of goodwill etc require more detailed analysis to form an opinion on ROIC. Inmarsat on the other side provided 11.81% ROIC. Whilst Vodafone still manage to provide positive return of 31.30%, Inmarsat shares outperformed at 114.98%.

11) Utilities:

Utilities exhibited low dispersion of ROA which not surprising given regulated nature of the industry. National Grid Plc had average ROIC of 13.27% whilst Severn Trent had ROIC of 7.08%. Stock market performance was on the opposite side with Severn Trent delivering 35.29% as opposed to 5.16% for National Grid.

Following analysis of industry performance a natural question arises whether there is systematic link between industry position in the FTSE 100 index, firm position in industry and shareholder returns delivered by this firm.

COMPANY	RISE SINCE 1/1/01 - 12/04/10	Strong industry	Strong firm
BHP Billiton	708%	√	√
BG Group	314%	√	√
British American Tobacco	291%	√	√
SABMiller	284%	√	

Imperial Tobacco	283%	√	√
Reckitt Benckiser	268%	√	√
Rio Tinto	259%	√	
Anglo American	193%	√	
Rolls-Royce	188%	Not in FTSE	Not in FTSE
Marks & Spencer	110%	√	√

The table above provides illustration to the link between shareholder return from 1/01/01 up till mid-April 2010 (before latest substantial correction) and the position of the firms which substantially outperformed the market and other companies in FTSE 100. The table was compiled from the FTSE 100 list as at 1/01/2001. Additionally industry positions and firms positions in industry were marked in accordance with the following principles:

- Industries were segmented and ranked in accordance with ROA compared to average. Accordingly industries with above-median ROA were ranked as “strong”. This list included Health Care (13.32%), Basic Materials (11.98%), Consumer Goods (11.01%), Oil & Gas (9.9%) and Consumer Services (9.12%). Industrials (8.88%) was borderline median case.
- Within industries similar exercise was undertaken to segment and rank firms.
- Industries and firms were marked or otherwise as “strong” in the table above.

On the basis of analysis above the following conclusions can be made:

- Not a single firm from the industry not considered as above average made it to the list of top performing firms.
- Majority of firms on the list above both came from above-average industry AND were among top firms in the industry.
- Where firms were above median firms but not top 3 firms (as is the case with Rio Tinto and Anglo-American) the firms had to deliver excellent ROIC (15.03% for Anglo American and 18.80% for Rio Tinto).
- The key to outperformance for majority of firms was consistent out-performance vis-à-vis index as demonstrated by table below. Some companies have been unable to clear the hurdle for additional “best in class” outperformance (Tesco, Standard Chartered) or experienced declines and were either relegated from the index (BAE System).

This is further supported by new companies joining “best-in-class” performers (over 5-years) as represented by Admiral Group (236.47%), Fresnillo (164.91%), Antofagasta (343.95%), Intertek (146.61%). All these firms also meet criteria above.

At the same time, very limited number of companies either exhibited excellent performance whilst not fully meeting criteria above (Sabmiller have consistently beat the index 9 out of 10 years and delivered 284% return over 10 years whilst its ROA being only 54% that of Diageo) or not performing well (GSK provided negative 14.85% return over 5 years despite being in top ROA industry with maximum firm return). A potential explanation could be offered in that FTSE 100 does not provide sufficient number of benchmark firms to compare Sabmiller and GSK with – only effectively one firm (respectively Diageo and Astrazeneca) per industry. This is in turn due to the fact that relevant best-in-class competitors are quotes elsewhere and are not part of FTSE.

Therefore inclusion of such competitors might effectively reposition Sabmiller and GSK in their relevant industry compared to competitors which can in turn account such performance. In addition whilst efficient market hypothesis would argue that firms were initially fairly valued it could be that initial “counting point” as of 1/01/2001 did not provide fair market valuation which made firm either under/valued (Sabmiller) or overvalued (GSK) with valuation converging to fair value over time.

Number of occasions a share has beaten the market for the 68 companies in the FTSE 100 at 1 January 2001 that are still trading today (Source: Bloomberg).

COMPANY	FREQUENCY OF BEATING INDEX
SABMiller	9
BHP Billiton	8
Reckitt Benckiser	8
BG Group	7
British American Tobacco	7
Imperial Tobacco Group	7
Anglo American	7
Standard Chartered	7
Tesco	7
BAE Systems	7

Empirical analysis of performance variability

COV results developed from model equation

Industry	12.1	14.49%
Year	4.6	5.48%
Industry-year	8.3	9.89%
Firm	15.1	18.07%
Error	43.6	52.07%
Total	83.8	100.00%

Table above provides summary of COV estimation of model in order to examine existence and relative importance of various factors which impact performance of industries and firms.

Total 48% of firm performance has been explained by the model, which is in line with previous research. Hawawini et al. (2002) noted that errors reported previously ranged from 45% in Rumelt (1991) to 80% in Schmalensee (1985). The error reported in this study is thus at the lower range of previously reported errors.

The most substantial factors impacting firm performance are firm-specific and explained 18.07% of aggregate variation (37.71% of explained variation). This is in contrast with Schmalensee (1985) study, however is in line with Rumelt (1991), McGahan and Porter (1997) studies where firm effects accounted for 46.37%, 31.71% and 35.8% accordingly.

Stable industry effects explained 14.49% of aggregate variation (30.22% of explained variation), in addition industry-year interaction explained 9.89% of aggregate variation (20.64% of explained variation). This is broadly in line with Schmalensee (1985) (20%), McGahan and Porter (1997) (19%) but is higher than Rumelt (1991) who found stable industry effect of around 8%, and also then in Hawawini et al. (2002) (11.2%). Industry-year effect was broadly in line with Rumelt (1991), other studies did not model industry-year interaction.

In addition temporal effect of 5.48% was identified which accounted for interaction of all industries with the business cycle (11.43% in terms of explained variation). The only study which modeled temporal effect was that of McGahan and Porter (1997) which identified 2.4% effect. In this study the effect is higher both at the overall and industry level due to significant impact of economic crisis on all industries and firms (as confirmed by detailed statistical analysis above).

To summarise the findings of this study in relation to literature the results were balanced when compared to studies confirming results of resource-based view on one side (Rumelt (1991), Mauri and Michaels (1998), Hawawini et al. (2002) and proponents of economic school as represented by Schmalensee (1985), McGahan and Porter (1997). The findings were similar to Hansen and Wernerfelt (1989) in that both economic and organizational factors were important in explaining together about 50% of aggregate variation, however unlike Hansen and Wernerfelt (1989) who concluded that organizational factors explained about twice as much variation as economic factors, in this study relative importance was 18.07% for firm factors as opposed to 14.49% for stable industry effects.

The results from the COV analysis of the model are consistent with statistical analysis of FTSE 100 industry and constituent firms data which concluded that both industry and firm factors were important in indentifying successful performance. Moreover both industry and firm factors were essential for delivery of successful financial performance and its reflection in excellent returns for companies' shareholders.

In terms of the previous research both industry and firms mattered for the population of firms and period of time under observation as it was both 1) very difficult for even top performing firms in the “weak” industries to deliver top shareholder performance as well as 2) preventing marginal firms demonstrate excellent shareholder returns even when whole industry benefited from specific part of the economic cycle.

7 Conclusions and recommendations

This dissertation examined the sources of performance differences by applying theoretical and empirical tools developed by several authors in analyzing predominantly US firms to the set of major UK firms as represented by FTSE 100 index component companies to address one the long-standing and important issues in both theory and applied strategic management research of what drives companies’ performance.

By applying statistical tools and COV estimation of the model, consistent results were obtained which demonstrated importance of both industry and firm specific factors to:

- 1) Achieve good financial performances as measured by returns on assets and invested capital.
- 2) Achieve the primary goal of a firm which is consistently taken in both academia and business to be maximization of shareholder wealth.

The study demonstrated the importance of both firm-specific and industry factors, which accounted accordingly for 18.07% and 14.49% of aggregate variation (37.71% and 30.22% of explained variation). Such findings presented a more balanced view compared to most previous research in the area, in addition empirical examination focused on UK listed firms.

In addition, a link between firm performance and shareholder returns was examined in more detail and a number of observations were made specifying additional hurdles which need to be cleared by firms to deliver truly excellent shareholder returns. Whilst under efficient market hypothesis it is not possible to consistently identify specific companies using a set of financial indicators, a number of papers have been written on the subject identifying specific criteria which make outperformance more likely. Whilst this paper did not attempt to establish more direct link between firm performance and its stock market returns, it provided highlights of attributes necessary for such stock market performance, especially in the challenging conditions of both economic crisis and general underperformance of major stock indices.

The job of the manager is thus important in both identifying industries which can benefit from future developments, as well as positioning firm resources and capabilities to

achieve industry outperformance whilst managing to ensure such outperformance is translated into excellent shareholder returns.

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